

ABSTRACT

This review focuses on the advanced role of communication in hydro-diplomacy by introducing a new approach, a stepwise key aspect, and tools of hydro-diplomacy for making the region stable. In addition, the review attempt was made to explain an aspect of hydro-diplomacy in the river Nile basin with the impact of GERD. Hydro-diplomacy has the potential to become an effective platform for international cooperation in the face of many current and future global water challenges. The role of communication in hydro-diplomacy can be categorized into conflict prevention and peace promotion, dialogue and cooperation, and multiple stakeholders' engagement. The review explores new approaches for building hydro-diplomacy by enhancing global observatory and regional water centers. Moreover, successful hydro-diplomacy passes through visible key paths, which include identification of key themes, analysis of the current state, recognition of drive, and identification of possible water diplomacy actions. The visible key approach has the potential to support water diplomacy processes with the help of the distinction it makes between water and diplomacy focused activities as well as its consideration of tensions and related actions. The article also seeks to provide key aspects of hydro-diplomacy and can be facilitate by recognizing political, preventive, integrative, cooperative, and technical normative foundations of hydro diplomacy, diplomatic relations, interaction, and trust between parties with

principles of transboundary water cooperation. The principle of hydro-diplomacy is also a key instrument for solving the Nile River water dispute over GERD. The coordination shall be between Egypt and Ethiopia in all political, economic, and social fields through one integrated water management and rationalization of consumption of available water resources. This should be done through the establishment of media and awareness campaigns and the development of plans and programs for using advanced techniques for the development of water resources as well as the stability of the region.

Keywords: Hydro-diplomacy, Nile basin, Transboundary, GERD, Principle, Water management, Communication

1. INTRODUCTION

Hydro-diplomacy is a new field of diplomacy that focusing on close ties between the worlds of science and diplomacy with traditional diplomatic instruments. It is defined by its emphasis on water related topics like access to drinking water, water sanitation, water scarcity, flooding, etc. All these categories are included in the broader category of international water management (Tomalova et al., 2020). Hydro-diplomacy is also gaining increasing attention among both researchers and policy-makers. The interest is given that the concept brings together themes such as shifting geopolitics, and new types of diplomacy. It is based on the application of this new concept of regional

cooperation that creates dynamics of transboundary basin of an economic development (Marko et al., 2021).

Water management is a multifarious responsibility that extends to agriculture, national security, public health and other areas. A hydro-diplomacy that promotes efficient water management requires the involvement of different actors who need to understand the water dimension diplomatic situation. As needed, it can employ the tools of pre-emptive diplomacy, designed to head off critical international problems, and crisis management. That is why the cooperation of government officials with the scientific community is crucial to successful water diplomacy. The case of water management is very well suited for a study of the practice and communication on hydro-diplomacy (Tomalova et al., 2020).

Hydro-diplomacy aims not simply to understand water cooperation and conflict, but rather to cultivate sustainable and peaceful solutions for all water users. This characteristic is frequently overlooked in more technical approaches to water diplomacy. Hydro-diplomacy is inherently political and understood the art of managing interpersonal and international relations by government officials in the nation context. In general, it is thus a major issue on the diplomatic agenda of the governments.

2. DISCUSSION AND ANALYSIS ON HYDRO-DIPLOMACY

The role of communication on hydro-diplomacy is to catalyze technical water cooperation and, at the same time, use it as a means to develop good neighborly relations in politically sensitive areas (Kata

et al., 2017). The hydro-diplomacy model provides a powerful tool organizational processes at all levels, reducing the demand of the vital liquid through rational management and increasing the supply by diversification of uses and reuses. Under hydro-diplomacy, a domestic and cooperative infrastructure make an effective long-term peaceful coexistence process for water allocation (Ursula, 2007).

Hydro-diplomacy has the potential to become an effective platform for international cooperation in the face of many current and future global water challenges. It combines preventive and reactive measures, as well as the mediation and implementation of solutions. It is crucial for regional and world security. Hydro-diplomacy prioritizes the issues of reducing economic and political tensions between countries and prevent conflicts. In this reality, multinational corporations will play an increasingly important role (Adam, 2021).

2.1 Role of communication on hydro-diplomacy

Based on trends on hydro-diplomacy, the roles can be categorized into conflict prevention and peace promotion, dialogue and cooperation, and multiple stakeholders' engagement. It is obvious that water cooperation traditionally deals with technological answers while water diplomacy is more political and reaches beyond water. The authors Kata et al., 2017, suggested the following additional roles of communication on hydro diplomacy.

1. Conflict prevention and peace promotion: When looking at the aim of

water diplomacy pertaining to conflict prevention and peace promotion, it is found four interconnected purposes like reconciliation, integrated prevention with promoting peace, prevention and resolution of conflicts, and promotion of peace, security and stability. Hydro-diplomacy can help in reconciling and balancing these interests and negotiate solutions for people residing in different countries and advocating for more efficient water allocation in various sectors.

2. Effectively manage water resources: increasing dialogue and cooperation: The need for dialogue and cooperation emerges, because of the challenges posed by the decreased quantity of available freshwater, environmental stress, lack of water availability due to climate change, poor basin management, river diversion, arid ecosystems, diverging water use requirements by different economic sectors. Water can be a catalyst, and can offer the potential as platform for cooperation to mitigate the increased risk (Salman, 2015).

3. Engaging multiple stakeholders: Multi-track water diplomacy distinguishes various stakeholders within the water governance framework to ensure water security at multiple levels. It recognizes that information flows up and down, and links different diplomatic tracks to prevent environmental injustice. The inclusion of more actors can help broaden the scope and depth of understanding of the problems, which in turn can create more space for innovative solutions (Huntjens et al., 2016).

4. Improving foreign relations: Improving foreign relations as a purpose of hydro

diplomacy could become more important in the future if more governments recognized this issue to be higher on their political agenda. The potential of what water diplomacy could encompass will be broadened as the definition evolves. However, there is ample evidence on how water cooperation contributes to better relations between states beyond water. Water diplomacy can be successful when parties realize that non-collaboration is likely to result in worse outcomes for all involved (Sadoff and Grey, 2002).

The suggested hydro diplomacy successfully implements by take the action of different measurement approaches. The approach which envisions possible ways forward through path different steps which are identification of key themes, related actors, current state, recognition of drivers and related scenarios; and identification of possible water diplomacy actions. Water diplomacy as a practical approach provides the future of foreign policy and diplomacy, where water is likely to be of increasing importance (Marko et al., 2021).

2.2 New approaches for building hydro-diplomacy

New approaches on building water diplomacy have advanced role for peace, security and has aims to use water as a means to the end of peace-building as opposed to better water management. The benefits that can be derived through water cooperation, it was argued, can create the political space for addressing more contentious issues and provide an entry-point for broader peace-building processes. The think-tank roundtable report on February, 2017 at Geneva addressed the

subject of “New Models for Hydro-diplomacy” for peace and security which observed new approach for role of communication on water diplomacy that a broad range of political tools and technical instruments can be employed. To this end, the report advanced two new mechanisms. Ideally though, the global observatory would be a hub connected to all regional multilateral water centers and other relevant institutions that would share best practice. The two proposed structures would be wholly independent of one another.

1. The global observatory for hydro-diplomacy and peace

The global observatory on water and peace could fulfill address the core issue of the existing gap between technical and political cooperation, maintain separate leading research, maintain a panel expert from practitioner organizations, and provide the donor community with an overview of global activities in the sector. Moreover, hydro-diplomacy safe transboundary water projects from preventing negative environmental and social impacts. The global observatory for water and peace which can help facilitate the expansion of water cooperation for effective peace-building by highlighting the potential of using water for peace, matching governments with organizations and approaches practical benefit, capturing organizations that successfully work in the area and administering a select network of regional practitioner institutions that are focused on using water for peace.

2. Regional water center for hydro-diplomacy

A resilient, practical and transferable peace-building mechanism that will enable the core parties to a conflict to harness the potential of water for peace through the various stages of peace. Hydro-diplomacy from a basin perspective comprises a broad spectrum of activities ranging from the resolution and prevention of water conflicts which could be understood the core water diplomacy role of river basin organization. River basin organization employ a range of mechanisms to fulfil the water diplomacy role.

A regional multilateral water center model, specifically designed to harness the potential of water to assist a peace process. These resilient centers involving the core parties to a peace process at diplomatic and technical levels would support a series of confidence building initiatives around water by:

- Resilient diplomatic and technical conduits for dialogue and confidence building measures using water.
- Mandated to focus on a river basin, a water technology or a water threat as needs require
- Involve the core parties of a conflict at diplomatic and technical level.
- Refocusing existing organizations or developed anew.

2.3 Key aspects of hydro-diplomacy

Different authors suggested that the process of hydro-diplomacy considers the five aspects like political, preventive, integrative, cooperative and technical categories. Those lays the normative foundation for hydro-diplomacy, diplomatic relations, interaction and trust

between parties with principles of transboundary water cooperation (UN, 1997 and UNECE, 1992).

Political aspect: Hydro-diplomacy as a process of inherently political interactions that occur among different stakeholders, interests, positions, and agenda. The aspect thus links closely to politics and power relations between and also within the riparian states. Water diplomacy is here seen as a part of the broader political, and considering political goals that extend beyond basin boundaries (Hocking et al., 2012).

Preventive aspect: Preventive views of water diplomacy as an approach for peace mediation as well as conflict prevention and mitigation. In this way, the aspect includes both preventive (in terms of preventing future conflicts) and restorative elements (in terms of reconciliation and reduction of existing tensions). These two elements together make water as a preventive diplomacy with reasonable and equitable water use and considered as the foundation of water diplomacy that build regional stability and peace (Yildiz and Gunes, 2016).

Integrative aspect: Integrative aspect builds that water diplomacy as a process comprising of many stakeholders across multiple societal and thematic sectors in both formal and informal settings (Marko et al., 2021). The Integrative aspect emphasizes this crosscutting and connecting nature of hydro-diplomacy, and therefore links to integrated approaches related to both water and diplomacy, which including integrated water resources

management, water-energy-food security nexus, and multi-track diplomacy (Grech et al., 2018).

Cooperative aspect: Water diplomacy as a process that promotes on mutual cooperation and the idea of shared benefits for transboundary water cooperation. Water cooperation can be seen as an operative end product of the process of water diplomacy, with the very aim of the cooperation defined by the diplomatic process. This aspect makes use of concepts such as benefit sharing, cooperation and water governance frameworks (Dore et al., 2012).

Technical aspect: It is based on the recognition of technical track of water diplomacy that focuses on water as a resource and as a physical substance that generates the hydrological cycle. Water availability, allocation, and the related monitoring, management, and knowledge production processes are therefore in the core of this aspect (Klimes and Yaari, 2019).

Marko et al., 2021 suggested that those five aspects of water diplomacy can help to better understand the broad concept of water diplomacy, as they bring together on the key dimensions from the current water diplomacy literature. Out of the five aspects, the political and technical aspects cross-cut the entire concept: while the technical aspect emphasizes the role of water and related knowledge production processes as a subject of the diplomacy, the political aspect emphasizes the inherently political nature of the interaction between whether national or international hydro-diplomacy actors.

2.4 Key paths of hydro-diplomacy approach

The article suggested by Marko et al., 2021, a four-step approach provided for analyzing a given water diplomacy context and recognizing potential water diplomacy actions. The hydro-diplomacy approach aims to provide a general analytical framework and a useful analysis tool for an external actor (third-party facilitator) that seeks to understand better a certain water diplomacy context. Yet, the approach could also be suitable for the actual hydro-diplomacy actors, like intergovernmental organization as an additional to view the potential tensions and related actions in the context of water diplomacy. The approach has a strong temporal dimension, and consider both the historical trajectory and possible future paths forward.

Step 1: Identifying key water diplomacy themes and actors

The first step in the proposed approach is to identify the most relevant themes and related actors for the specific water diplomacy context. In addition to the use and development of shared water resource, typical themes to be considered include water related sectors like agriculture and energy as well as broader themes related to regional cooperation (trade, the environment, political relations). To ensure sufficient consideration of all relevant themes, the identification may be initiated by recognizing first broad regional settings, such as biophysical, societal and institutional and then identifying the key themes and actors for such hydro-diplomacy settings.

Step 2: Analyzing the current state

The second step aims to analyze the current state of the given water diplomacy context, building on the themes and actors recognized in Step 1. The analysis should preferably include also a consideration of the past trends, including those related to water use, infrastructure development and broader political relations between the riparian countries. Such historical trajectory deepens the understanding of the present situation and also helps to recognize alternative future paths in the following steps. The suggested method for this step includes a comparative analysis and joint synthesis of existing studies in this specific context, as it is likely that there already exists relevant information among the actors.

Step 3: Recognizing key drivers and related future scenarios

The third step seeks first to recognize key drivers (like, biophysical, social, economic and/or political) that are likely to impact the current status within a given timeframe. After, the step envisions possible future scenarios on how water-related interactions could unfold in a given context, based on a set of assumptions on how current state may evolve due to key drivers and evolving relationships between the parties.

Step 4: Identifying possible water diplomacy actions

The fourth step focuses on the identification of possible water diplomacy actions that build on the key drivers and future scenarios recognized from Step 3. The actions can thus strengthen the positive, mutually beneficial activities envisioned as well as to ease the possible water related and/or political tensions recognized in Step 3.

Given the varying aspects related to the approach of hydro- diplomacy.

2.5 Basic tools for communication on hydro-diplomacy

Hydro-diplomacy is a set of negotiating and diplomatic activities and that target specific water issues such that human efforts are mobilized, and allocation of material and symbolic capabilities are made during a specific period to achieve strategic goals at the international water level (Magdy, 2011). The negotiating teams should possess the following tools.

Languages: A good knowledge of the official language of all contesting parties is very important and at least an awareness of the language of the opposite party at the negotiating table. It is important to follow the media and measure the trends of public opinion to know the extent of pressure or support associated with the issue up for negotiation.

Philology: It is important for negotiators who are involved in discussions related to water to be aware of the jurisprudence of the language and to understand the written texts in the language of both parties. Negotiators should fall on historical agreements regarding the sharing of water between upstream and downstream countries, and the circumstances surrounding these agreements.

International law: Good knowledge of the international water law which consists of a set of principles and standards that provide practical tools for riparian states to determine solutions that are beneficial to all. This law reflects state practices and

aims at facilitating discussion and cooperation between them.

Geography: The most important sciences ever in water diplomacy matters; human geography, water geography, political geography, terrain sciences, and climate.

Cartography: the negotiator must be familiar with cartography, which helps in defining the inputs well and arriving at outputs within the framework of the agreement to achieve the purpose of what is required from hydro-diplomatic discussions.

2.6 Key reasons for making hydro-diplomacy

Water diplomacy is an approach that enables a variety of stakeholders to assess ways to contribute to finding solutions for joint management of shared freshwater resources. It is a dynamic process that seeks to develop reasonable, sustainable and peaceful solutions to water management while promoting or informing cooperation and collaboration among riparian stakeholders (Klimes et al., 2019).

2.7 Actors making for hydro-diplomacy

Water diplomacy in conflict-affected regions offers dialogue entry points different to more traditional conflict management mechanisms. There is a continuous demand for knowledge about water diplomacy and, in particular, about the linkages between political and technical tracks. The actors involved in multi-track water diplomacy can comprise various groups of state and non-state actors. Formal actors, mainly encompassing Ministry of Foreign Affairs, water line ministry, and other ministries and government agencies

according to the specific context are often the most visible.

Informal or non-state actors also have an important role in water diplomacy dialogues. Representatives of civil society organizations, academia and think tanks, media, and faith-based traditions all have an important role to play to build relations and contribute to shared knowledge on common water resources. External actors are also crucial and can range from multilateral and bilateral foreign policy and development partners including UN agencies to regional organizations, and international financial institutions. To increase chances of success, these processes should be broad and inclusive, with a clear gender focus. Having a diverse cross-section of stakeholders participating in dialogues around shared waters ensures that the impacts and benefits of shared water management are identified early, increasing the likelihood of equitable solutions to the prevention of conflict relapse.

3. TRANSBOUNDARY OF WATER MANAGEMENT FOR ENHANCING OF HYDRO-DIPLOMACY

The issue of conflicts over water resources in transboundary river basins has recently become a focal point for political studies. Water resource management is inherently a complex political process, which reflects the balance between environmental, economic, and social values of water (Butterworth et al. 2010). This happens through the determination of water allocation, uses, related norms, and ultimately water rights. Thus, natural resource management and politics are strictly interconnected. Increased pressure

on trans boundary water resources resulting from growing economic and population demands, amplified by climate change processes can have devastating effects in regions affected by armed conflicts and internal water mismanagement (Hussam, 2017).

The Benjamin et al., 2014 provided the following objectives to facilitating the containment of hydro-diplomacy and resolution of conflicts in the short term so that conflicts are avoided in the longer term, and harnessing the water cooperation for the purpose of stronger regional integration. Progress on these fronts will face many challenges; three in particular stand out:

Facilitating agency: First and most fundamentally, there is a lack of agency at the international level. Our call for more agency is not about creating new organizations, but about establishing institutional setting that connects pivotal actors, reinforces, complements existing frameworks, initiatives, expertise to coordinate and execute political action. Its purpose should be ensured systematic early warning and support coordinated action.

Improving coordination: Second, there is a need for a more coordinated and strategic approach among external actors. They need to engage jointly, with a particular focus from whichever actor has the most leverage in a given situation. The need for closer cooperation applies not only to cooperation between, but also within governments.

Enabling actors: Third, there are a number of capacity-related problems that hinder greater cooperation on transboundary waters. The international community and

individual donors can undertake a number of specific policies to develop institutional, human, financial capacities to enable basin stakeholders and external actors to contain the risks and harness the opportunities of engaging on transboundary water governance.

4. ASPECTS OF HYDRO-DIPLOMACY ON THE RIVER OF NILE BASIN

Water diplomacy across international borders can be a useful tool in solving problems related to the shared water resources of the political entities involved, especially when the interests of the countries are diverse. Water disputes can likely lead to potential conflicts if not properly address in a holistic manner to satisfy all parties concerned. Many discussions about water resources that cut across international borders have focused on their potential for either conflict or cooperation. The article suggested by Francis, 2022, analyzed the concept of water diplomacy and look the dispute over the Nile River, while highlighting the legitimate right of Egypt, Ethiopia, and Sudan in line with international conventions on water resources.

The Nile is a well-known and long river, though relatively modest in terms of volume. Flows are uneven across the Nile Basin and are often impacted upon by extreme climatic events. The main hydraulic and political features of the basin, however, are the asymmetric use of water resources. The downstream riparian's (Egypt and Sudan) have consolidated their control over water resources. Egypt is the most powerful state in the basin; it has

achieved a substantial degree of hydraulic, legal and political control over the Nile waters (Ana, 2008).

4.1 International dispute on hydro-diplomacy

Despite the improvement of political relations between the three countries its reflection on understanding and cooperation are still limited in reaching a final and fair agreement for the water resources. This issue is still a hotbed of tension between the riparian countries, as Egypt sees the actions of Ethiopia as contravene to international agreement of which Ethiopia claims was not a party. Besides, hydro-diplomatic efforts haven't achieved its goal to solve the dispute to reach a final agreement, and the main reason is that the entrenched position taken by all parties on the territorial right to the Nile River. The political history of the region confirms that the freshwater variable has become an essential component of security as it is an important factor in the economy. Many proposals were made in which this dispute could be resolved after setbacks of diplomatic attempts (Taya, 2006). Among the proposals include:

1. Egypt, Ethiopia, and Sudan solution and the principle of good-neighborliness

Egypt, Ethiopia and Sudan all have concern that the dispute has a political dimension to it and requires a political decision at the highest level due to its interwoven and association with other problems (Abdulaziz, 1996). Their suggestion to resolve the problem was to refrain Ethiopia from cutting down the volume of water supply to Egypt and the possibility of flooding in Sudan when the dam become

fully operationalized. Furthermore, all countries called for a resolution of the water dispute with a good intention, relying on norms and international law and the principle of good neighborliness (Tariq, 1994). The first and basic step towards resolution of the crises adopted by the Egypt-Ethiopian side was for Ethiopia to ensure that the volume of water required by Egypt will not be reduced once the dam becomes operationalized at full capacity level of the dam.

At the same time basin serious and urgent discussions between the riparian countries at the foreign ministry level must continue to ensure agreement on the final distribution of the basin water, and investment terms” (Jamalou, 1996). However, the Egypt attitude toward the Nile River is still unchanged and insistence of the colonial agreement. Egypt considered the problem as a technical issue, which can be solved according to the principle of apportioning water usage, Egypt also saw no need for the adoption of international law or the laws adopted by the General Assembly (Zakaria, 1994). Egypt also asserts there are protocols, notes, and meetings between the basin countries that confirm the internationalism of the two rivers, and Ethiopia have recognized in more than one treaty that the two rivers are international and subject to international law like, protocol 1987 between Egypt and Sudan, which is registered with the General Secretariat of the UN on 1 June 1993. Egypt insists if Ethiopia continues to reject the international feature of the rivers, then the Rhine, Senegal, the Nile, and other rivers

will not be considered as international rivers (Jamalou, 1996).

The preliminary agreement by all bordering countries on the construction of the Grand Renaissance Dam in February 2015, seems to be a step in the right direction on the share of the Nile water, however, future cooperation will determine the future of Egypt-Ethiopia-Sudan relations until they all reach a final agreement, settlements that guarantee each state with its water rights according to the international agreements on water distribution. The author Francis, 2022 set of many recommendations to resolve conflicts on sharing of Nile river water resources:

1. The importance of coordination between Egypt and Ethiopia in all political, economic, and social fields through one integrated water management, and rationalization of consumption of available water resources. This should be done through the establishment of media and awareness campaigns, and the development of plans and programs for using advanced techniques for the development of water resources.
2. Activating diplomatic channels between the riparian countries to conclude a tripartite agreement, based on the recommendations from conferences, water bodies, and international law. Negotiating teams with a specialty in legal, economic, and technical skills are to be formed to reach a final agreement that preserves the water rights for all parties.
3. Activate the African Union's diplomatic and political effort at the regional and international levels to ensure and protect

Nile water interests and enhance negotiating capabilities for shared waters with all countries, provided this is done based on the rules of international law and agreements.

4. Mobilization of international forces to internationalize the water crisis and advocate for the water rights due Ethiopia and Sudan. International and legal organizations must step up to take a stand that Egypt's insistence has no international legal basis because, from a legal standpoint, the principle of not harming others can not apply without specifying the share due to each of the three riparian countries in the basin.

4.2 Key reason of Ethiopia building GERD

Egypt's concern on the current dispute is the volume of water supply once the dam becomes fully operationalized. Egypt needs assurance from Ethiopia that its required volume of water will not be disrupted by Ethiopia's dam. Water supply from the Nile is vital to all the country's concerns and the construction of critical infrastructure is equally vital to the long-term development agenda of the region. With this in mind demand for critical projects are very important for the population. The table below, therefore, highlights electricity accessibility supply among Egypt, Ethiopia, and Sudan from 2016-2020 (Francis, 2022).

Table 1: Highlights population and access to electricity by the competing countries

Countries	Population, million	2016, %	2017, %	2018, %	2019, %	2020, %
Ethiopia	114.96	43	44	45	48	45
Sudan	42.81	49	51	52	54	54
Egypt	100.4	100	100	100	100	100

(Sources: World bank data. (<https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/EG.ELC.ACCS.ZS?locations=ET>))

Egypt from 2016 to 2021 is the only country among the three Nile basin countries that enjoy 100% access to electricity by the entire population. Every part of Egypt enjoys uninterrupted access to electricity provision for 24 hours per day. Ethiopia and Sudan on the other hand are handicapped with access to electricity coverage. Ethiopians continue to lack access to electricity. As shown in the table from 2016-2021 about 50% of the entire Ethiopian population does not have access to electricity and this according to development expertise affects the flow of foreign direct investments and development agenda of Ethiopia. Availability of electricity is seen as one of the tools for accelerated development and attraction of foreign direct investment.

According to Ethiopian sources the primary motive for the construction of the Grand Renaissance dam is to provide the needed electricity for the Ethiopians and to relieve the country of the acute energy shortage and also to export electricity to neighboring countries. Ethiopians' development agenda is that the construction of the Dam will increase electricity accessibility to over 80% of the entire population of Ethiopia.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This article explains the role of communication on hydro-diplomacy and argues that the hydro-diplomacy approach to transboundary water resources which is a key instrument for making peaceful environment on riparian countries. Hydro-diplomacy has the potential to become an

effective platform for international cooperation in the face of many current and future global water challenges. It combines preventive and reactive measures, as well as the mediation and implementation of solutions. It is crucial for regional and world security. Hydro-diplomacy also across international borders can be a useful tool in solving problems related to the shared water resources of the political entities involved, especially when the interests of the countries are diverse. Water disputes can likely lead to potential conflicts if not properly address in a holistic manner to satisfy all parties concerned. Many discussions about water resources that cut across international borders have focused on their potential for either conflict or cooperation. On the context of Great Ethiopian Renaissance Dam, Egypt, Sudan and Ethiopia should keep their commitment to expanding a mutual understanding in order to enhance the cooperation of Nile basin countries should be a priority for both Egypt and Ethiopia. Their role in the family of Nile basin nations should be active and positive.

Generally, on the sharing of Nile river water resources, it should develop the communication of hydro-diplomacy and set the following recommendations to resolve conflicts.

- The importance of coordination between Egypt and Ethiopia in all political, economic, and social fields through one integrated water management, and rationalization of consumption of available water resources.
- Activating diplomatic channels between the riparian countries to conclude a tripartite agreement, based on the recommendations from conferences, water bodies, and international law.
- Activate the African Union's diplomatic and political effort at the regional and international levels to ensure and protect Nile water interests and enhance negotiating capabilities for shared waters with all countries, provided this is done based on the rules of international law and agreements.
- Mobilization of international forces to internationalize the water crisis and advocate for the water rights due Ethiopia and Sudan.

REFERENCES

Abdulaziz, A., 1996. The Reality of the Water Problem between Syria and Iraq with Turkey. *Journal of Palestine's voice*, Damascus. 240, 22.

Adam K., 2021. Water Diplomacy and Its Strategic Significance for Sustainable Development Goals and Global Security Architecture. *Sustainability* 2021, 13, 13898. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su132413898>.

Ana E., 2008. Ethiopia challenges to Egyptian hegemony in the Nile Basin. *Water Policy*. 2, 13-28.

Benjamin P., Ken C., Geoffrey D., and Anika K., 2014. The rise of hydro-diplomacy. Strengthening transboundary waters. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/267327771>.

Butterworth, J., 2010. Local approaches to integrated water resources management. *Water Alternatives*. 3, 68.

Dore, J., Lebel, L., and Molle, F., 2012. A framework for analyzing transboundary water governance complexes, illustrated in the Mekong Region. *Journal of hydrology*. 466, 23–36.

Francis K., 2022. Water diplomacy and the share of the Nile River between Egypt, Ethiopia and Sudan. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*. 13,1.

Global High-Level Panel on Water and Peace, 2017. *Hydro-Diplomacy for Water, Peace and Security Beyond Shared Water Management*. Think-Tank Roundtable Report in Geneva, February 2017.

Grech M., Oring, S., Kim, K., and Swain, A., 2018. Negotiating water across levels: A peace and conflict “Toolbox” for water diplomacy. *Journal of hydrology*. 559, 100–109.

Hocking, B., Melissen, J., Riordan, S., and Sharp, P., 2012. *Futures for diplomacy, integrative diplomacy in the 21st Century* (Clingendael, Netherlands Institute of International Relations).

Huntjens, P., Yasuda, Y., Swain, A., Deman, R., Magsig, B., and Islam, S., 2016. *The Multi-track water diplomacy framework. Analysis for Advancing Cooperation over Shared Waters*. The Hague institute for global justice. <http://www.thehagueinstituteforglobaljustice.org/wp-content/>.

Hussam M., 2017. *Dynamic political contexts and power asymmetries: the cases of the Blue Nile and the Yarmouk Rivers*. Springer journal. 17, 795–814.

Jamalou A., 1996. *Water dispute in the ME*. Riyad Al-Rayes for books and publishing, Beirut, 46.

Kata M., Rosa C., Susanne S., Siegfried D., 2017. *Preventing conflicts, fostering cooperation. The many roles of water diplomacy*. UNESCO ‘s international centre for water cooperation (ICWC) at SIWI, Stockholm, Sweden and the UNESCO ‘s International Centre for Water Resources and Global Change (ICWRGC), Koblenz, Germany.

Klimes, M., Michel, D., Yaari, E., and Restiani, P., 2019. Water diplomacy, the intersect of science, policy and practice. *Journal of hydrology*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2019.02.049>.

Klimes, M., and Yaari, E., 2019. *Water diplomacy. Facilitating dialogues* (Stockholm International Water Institute SIWI).

Magdy, H., 2011. *Water Diplomacy a tool for enhancing water peace and sustainability in the Arab region*. Second Arab water forum theme 3: Sustainable and fair solutions for the transboundary rivers and groundwater aquifers. 21.

Marko K., Erik S., and Juho H., 2021. *Water diplomacy paths, an approach to recognize water diplomacy actions in shared waters*. *Journal of Hydrology*. <http://creativecommons.org/licenses>.

Salman, A. 2015. *Blue Diplomacy, transboundary water governance from a foreign policy lens*. Policy Brief Publication Series Regional Green Dialogs. Pakistan. <https://af.boell.org/sites/default>.

Sadoff, C., and Grey, D., 2002. Beyond the river: the benefits of cooperation on international rivers. *Water policy*. 4, 389–403.

Tariq, A., 1994. Arab-Turkish cooperation in the field of infrastructure projects, water and electrical Energy. *Journal of Arab Future*, Beirut. 188, 80.

Taya M., 2006. Limited water resources and international conflict, a survey study of theoretical trends. *Journal of Al-Nahda*, Cairo University. 7,2.

Tomalova, E., Cernovska, E., Aukes, J., and Montana, E., 2020. Water diplomacy and its future in the national, regional, European and Global environments. *Science diplomacy in the making: Case-based insights from the S4D4C project*.

Ursula, 2007. *Hydro-Diplomacy: Opportunities for Learning from an Interregional Process*. *Integrated Water Resources Management and Security in the Middle East*, 163–200.

UNECE, 1992. *The Convention on the Protection and Use of Transboundary Watercourses and International Lakes*.

UN, 1997. *Convention on the Law of the Non navigational Uses of International Watercourses*.

Yildiz, D., and Gunes, M., 2016. New security concept and analytical transdisciplinary approaches to hydro politics. *International journal Sci. Eng. Res.* 8, 297–316.

Zakaria A., 1994. *Water in international law and the Arab water crisis*. Damascus, Translation and Publishing Dar Tlas for Studies. 130.